

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF USING DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract. Digitization of all areas of our life today, including the role of digital technologies in preschool and primary education, the role of digital technologies in training future primary school teachers, the challenges of modern education. drawn up. The positive and negative aspects of the introduction of digital technologies in primary education, features and opportunities of primary education, the importance of digital technologies in primary education, requirements for their rational and effective use are presented. The article discusses the current problems of the theory and methodology of the use of information and communication technologies and digital technologies as a means of the modern educational process that increases the cognitive activity, worldview and motivation of children of preschool and primary school age, which is considered an important need of the current era of globalization. In the current conditions, a modern school needs teachers who have knowledge and skills in using information and communication technologies in their professional activities, who have well-formed information and communication competence (IEC). The use of digital technologies in the process of education and upbringing guarantees the achievements of children of preschool age and the guarantees of successful studies at school later.

Key words: education, personnel, information and communication technologies, digital technology, cognitive activity, primary education, digitization.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДИКИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ЦИФРОВЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ

Аннотация. Цифровизация всех сфер нашей жизни сегодня, в том числе роль цифровых технологий в дошкольном и начальном образовании, роль цифровых технологий в подготовке будущих учителей начальных классов, сформулированы задачи современного образования. Представлены положительные и отрицательные стороны внедрения цифровых технологий в начальное образование, особенности и возможности начального образования, значение цифровых технологий в начальном образовании, требования к их рациональному и эффективному использованию. В статье рассматриваются актуальные проблемы теории и методологии использования информационно-коммуникационных технологий и цифровых технологий как средства современного образовательного

процесса, повышающего познавательную активность, мировоззрение и мотивацию детей дошкольного и младшего школьного возраста. считается важной потребностью нынешней эпохи глобализации. В современных условиях современной школе необходимы учителя, обладающие знаниями и навыками использования информационно-коммуникационных технологий в своей профессиональной деятельности, обладающие сформированной информационно-коммуникативной компетенцией (ИОК). Использование цифровых технологий в процессе обучения и воспитания гарантирует достижения детей дошкольного возраста и гарантии успешной учебы в школе в дальнейшем.

Ключевые слова: образование, кадры, информационно-коммуникационные технологии, цифровые технологии, познавательная деятельность, начальное образование, цифровизация.

As a result of the scientific and technical development in the world, the emergence of new fields in the sciences and the rapid development of interdisciplinary integration lead to an increase in the requirements for information, in particular, knowledge, skills and qualifications in the process of training specialists in the higher education system. In such conditions, the problems of introducing innovative and integrated technologies in the process of training future teachers, strictly following the principles of interdisciplinarity in the transmission of information are emerging. As a result, it is necessary to improve the innovative and integrated technologies of the training process of future elementary school teachers in higher educational institutions. On a global scale, research is being conducted aimed at forming ideas about the content of the training of future teachers, the laws of existence and development of the real world as a social and natural whole, the main connections between its elements and the nature of relations. In particular, the specific characteristics of the problem of developing innovative thinking, the problems of innovation and integration in the process of educational organization, and the results of research on the theoretical issues of integration are important. At the same time, enriching the knowledge, skills and qualifications of future primary school teachers with innovative and integrative technologies of organizing the educational process, including information about the laws of integration processes, is becoming an urgent task. . In our country, special attention is paid to the issues of improving the system of pedagogic personnel training, increasing the quality of education in general education schools, stratification, variable curricula, wide implementation of the principles of preparing students for life in the teaching of subjects. "Introduction of the theory and methodology of the use of information and communication technologies and digital technologies as a means of the

modern educational process for educational directions and specialties in the field of pedagogy ..." tasks are defined, and the mental, intellectual and physical strength of the student is determined by digital technologies. directing to a specific goal, supplementing practical activities with theoretical knowledge, developing knowledge, design, communicative-speech and organizational knowledge and skills using information and communication technologies and digital technologies, theoretical knowledge, practical knowledge and requires the development of scientifically based proposals and recommendations for improving effective mechanisms of interdisciplinary integration based on innovative approaches aimed at skill formation. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 ", dated October 8, 2019 "Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847, dated July 6, 2022, "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system until 2030" Decree No. PF-60, dated June 5, 2018, "Additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country" on" No. PQ-3775, No. PQ-289 of June 21, 2022 "On measures to increase the quality of pedagogical education and further develop the activities of higher educational institutions that train pedagogues" It serves to implement the tasks defined in its decisions and other normative legal documents related to this field.

It is not a secret to anyone that the specific features of using information and communication technologies and digital technologies, pedagogical conditions, and their use in primary classes are of particular importance in the training of future primary school teachers. Digital technologies are a system of tools that is rapidly and rapidly developing in our time, developing as one of the current but very effective methods. The team of teachers is making strong efforts to implement the use of information and communication technologies and digital technologies in educational technologies as a means of the modern educational process. The main essence of pedagogical creativity depends on the purpose and nature of pedagogical activity. Pedagogical activity is the process of solving a number of pedagogical problems that are subject to the common goal of forming a person's personality, worldview, faith, mind, and character. The creative activity of the teacher is manifested in the search for educational methods and the ability to find solutions to these problems. The source of pedagogical creativity is pedagogical experience. Pedagogical experience is full of problematic situations. Advanced pedagogical experience means a teacher's creative approach to his task, searching for and using new and effective methods and tools in teaching and educating students. Currently, digital pedagogy is a very important issue. Its main characteristic is demonstrability, openness, consistency. The only objective requirement is the level of knowledge about the intellectual development and upbringing of a person. News, as

well as the formation of new ideas, is based on initiative and digital technology, aimed at improving the content of education. In general, this has a positive effect on the development of learning structures and procedures. Enrichment of modern pedagogical technologies with information technologies not only changes and improves existing teaching methods and technologies, but also computers, tablets, software and hardware, video and telecommunications, special equipment, as well as various data processing forms news related to the use of systems. The laws and features of the implementation of pedagogical integration in the selection of goals and tasks require the logical content of the integration, which is carried out to ensure the unity of ideas, to strengthen knowledge on the basis of a single teaching methodology and tools. Along with the effective development of students' knowledge, their cognitive abilities, activity, interests and intellectual potential increase in the conditions of interdisciplinary connection in the educational process. The integration of subjects in the educational process, i.e. interdisciplinary communication, ensures the effective development of students' knowledge, as well as their cognitive abilities, activities, interests, and intelligence. The possibility of interdisciplinary communication in educational lessons prepares students to analyze facts, understand the nature of cause and effect in the study of events and processes, apply previously acquired knowledge to new situations , and also increases the integration of subjects in the elementary school.

The choice of the form of learning new material in the lesson depends on the level of the participants, the characteristics and level of preparation of the children, the features of the subject, the possibilities of the audience, the modern educational process tools, information and communication technologies and digital technologies , the skills of the teacher, etc.

By organizing classes using modern educational process, information and communication technologies and digital technologies, we will have the following advantages:

- ❖ more favorable conditions are created for the development of various intellectual skills of students;
- ❖ students get a more integrated picture of the perception of the world, the surrounding reality;
- ❖ teaching periods of individual subjects will be reduced;
- ❖ the main components of educational activity, that is, the desire and ability to learn are formed;
- ❖ the ability to study the interrelationship of materials on different topics as a whole is developed;
- ❖ development of mental activity is carried out;
- ❖ a wide opportunity is created to develop students' speech and broaden their worldview;

- ❖ strengthens the desire to learn and enriches positive moral qualities;
- ❖ an opportunity to fully demonstrate the diversity of the world, involving scientific knowledge, literature, painting, music, etc.

The use of information and communication technologies and digital technologies in primary education, based on providing students with selected educational tasks, taking into account their individual abilities and interests, allows the teacher to rely on the results of previous activities, compare them, and perform the next educational task. allows to organize in such a way as to create an emotionally oriented conscious need.

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